

D6.1. TRAIN-THE-TRAINERS ACTION REPORT WP6

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

The project CARE4DIABETES has received funding from the European Commission under GA No 101082427.

Technical References

Deliverable No.	D6.1
Dissemination Level ¹	PU — Public
Work Package	Work Package 6: Phase I implementation (capacity building oriented)
Lead beneficiary	CSPA
Version	V4
Due date of deliverable	31 January 2024
Submission date	25 January 2024
Revision date	19 December 2024 This version (V4) has been updated after the deliverable due date considering the suggestions received by experts during the project monitoring process performed by HADEA.

Versions

Version	Person	Partner	Date
V1	Marta Pisano González / Isabel Diez Valcarce, Cristina Fernández García / Elvira Llana Suárez, María Escibano Santamarina, Raquel Ochoa González	CSPA / SESPA / FICYT	9 January 2024
V1.1	Charlotte Jutton, Stefanie Vandevijvere	Sciensano	11 January 2024
V1.2	Jelka Zaletel, Denis Oprešnik, Anja Brunec	NIJZ	17 January 2024
V2	Marta Pisano González / Isabel Diez Valcarce, Cristina Fernández García / Elvira Llana Suárez, Raquel Ochoa González	CSPA / SESPA / FICYT	19 January 2024
V3	Marta Pisano González / Isabel Diez Valcarce, Cristina Fernández García / Elvira Llana Suárez, Raquel Ochoa González	CSPA / SESPA / FICYT	21 November 2024
V4	María Escibano Santamarina, Marta Pisano González / Raquel Ochoa González, Elvira Llana Suárez, / Isabel Diez Valcarce, Cristina Fernández García	CSPA/ FICYT / SESPA	19 December 2024

Acknowledgements. Voeding Leeft are kindly thanked for their work and contributions in the training of trainers developed in the framework of this project.

¹ PU = Public
SEN = Sensitive

Approved by Coordinator on: 13/01/2025

Approved by Quality Manager on: 13/01/2025

Disclaimer. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Train-the-trainers action report

Table of contents

GLOSSARY / LIST OF ACRONYMS.....	2
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1. PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES	6
2. METHODOLOGY	6
2.1. Organizational aspects of the training.....	7
2.2. Roles of the multidisciplinary team and number of professionals.....	8
2.3. Description of the intervention	9
2.4. Description of the content of the VL trainings.....	11
2.5. Preparatory actions and materials	18
2.6. Completion of the trainings and evaluation.....	21
3. RESULTS.....	24
4. CONCLUSIONS	31
5. REFERENCES.....	32
6. ANNEXES.....	33
Annex 1. Agendas of the VL training.....	33
Annex 2. Overview of VL training materials	47
Annex 3. Example materials shared by Voeding Leeft	58

GLOSSARY / LIST OF ACRONYMS

Term	Definition
C4D team	It is the core team of C4D JA in collaborative learning and knowledge generation which eliminates bottlenecks during the implementation of C4D practice, provides strategic vision and supports implementation process through the focus of the system, sustainability, scalability of the practice.
Grant Agreement	Funding agreement concluded between the European Commission/ funding agency and the project participants, which specifies the rights and obligations of the contracting parties.
Implementing countries	12 EU countries (Bulgaria, Belgium, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia and Spain), implementing C4D practice.
Phase 1 / Phase 2	Refers to the 6-month intensive care (Phase 1) and 6-month aftercare / follow-up (Phase 2) intervention.
Pilot implementers	They are engaged in the transfer and implementation of the best practice in implementing countries.
Program Coordinator	Reference person responsible of the development of the VL BP for each participant.
Round A / Round B	It refers to the two consecutive groups of T2D patients taking part in the intervention, Round A starting at M12 and Round B at M21.
VL best practice	The best practice selected for this JA is the “Reverse Diabetes2 Now experience” (RD2N). It is an evidence-based and reimbursed Dutch lifestyle treatment and training program for type 2 diabetes, developed and promoted by the Dutch non-profit organisation Voeding Leeft.
Acronym	Description
ADA	American Diabetes Association
BP	Best Practice
C4D JA	CARE4DIABETES Joint Action: Reducing the burden of non-communicable diseases by providing a multi-disciplinary lifestyle treatment intervention for type 2 diabetes
CSPA	Consejería de Salud del Principado de Asturias., in English “Regional Ministry of Health in Asturias”
EASD	European Association for the Study of Diabetes
FICYT	Fundación para la promoción de las Ciencias Aplicadas a la Investigación y la Tecnología, in English “Foundation for the Promotion of Applied Scientific Research and Technology in Asturias”
GA	Grant Agreement
GP	General Practitioner
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IT	Information technology
JA	Joint Action
M	Month, calculated from the start of the project (M1=February 2023)
MDT	Multidisciplinary Team
N/A	Not available
PDSA	Plan-Do-Study-Act

RD2N	Reverse Diabetes 2 Now
SESPA	Servicio de Salud del Principado de Asturias, in English the “Regional Health System of Asturias”
THL	Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare
T2D	Type 2 diabetes
VL	Voeding Leeft
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is the first deliverable of the work package 6 (WP6) “Phase I implementation (capacity building oriented)”. This deliverable integrates information related to task 6.2 “*Training the trainers*” on the C4D program developed between month M1 and M11 of the project, as described in the Grant Agreement (GA) of the Joint Action “*Reducing the burden of non-communicable diseases by providing a multi-disciplinary lifestyle treatment intervention for type 2 diabetes (CARE4DIABETES)*” (C4D JA).

The C4D JA supports 12 Member States in reducing the burden of type 2 diabetes (T2D) through effective lifestyle treatment programs. Partners will implement a Dutch evidence-based best practice (BP) “Reverse Diabetes 2 Now” (RD2N), developed by the non-governmental organisation Voeding Leeft (VL) in the Netherlands. The specific objectives of the pilot intervention phase are:

- ✓ To enhance lifestyle counselling knowledge and skills among healthcare professionals involved in the project pilots.
- ✓ To transfer, pilot, evaluate and adjust a lifestyle intervention model for T2D patients in each implementing country.
- ✓ To improve lifestyle, quality of life and levels of glycaemic control and reduction in use of glucose-lowering medication among T2D participants.
- ✓ To integrate the lifestyle intervention model for T2D patients into local/regional/national health care services.

The **purpose** of the document is to summarise the C4D “Train-the-trainers” training received from the BP owner (i.e., VL), by the implementing partners from the 12 different countries involved (Belgium, Bulgaria, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia and Spain) to acquire the knowledge to implement the pilot actions. Also, actions developed to transmit, when possible, to other health professionals in their respective country in their own language are presented.

The **objective** of this deliverable is to describe the organization, development of the “Train-the-trainers” training of local healthcare and their evaluation. Key outcomes will feed D3.2 Interim evaluation report in WP3.

The intended audience are all members of the C4D consortium (competent authorities and affiliated entities), especially the WP leaders, C4D teams from implementing countries, stakeholders involved in the pilot implementation and/or dissemination and scale-up of the VL BP, and other entities interested in gaining knowledge of the BP to be implemented in their settings.

The methodology was developed by the VL team, based on their experience along the years of implementation in the Netherlands. The Coordination Team of the C4D JA (CSPA, SESPA and FICYT) has collaborated to organise the different cluster groups participating in each edition.

In **conclusion**, this document describes how multidisciplinary teams from each participant country are organised and engage in their respective capacity building process to get ready to reproduce the VL BP in their regions/countries.

The work expected under this deliverable was carried out on time and without deviations, and all the countries participating in the Joint Action were involved.

1. PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this document is to compile and describe the content of the BP program, 3 different rounds of trainings organized by VL, including the updates and improvements considered from one edition, based on the appraisals received by the pilot implementers and WP3 leaders (Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare, THL) who are responsible for any evaluation process related to the C4D JA.

The objective of the D6.1 is to describe how VL has transmitted to C4D JA partners the knowledge about the BP to adapt, adopt, abandon or add elements necessary to implement it in their respective regions/countries.

2. METHODOLOGY

Voeding Lefst (VL), in collaboration with the coordination team (The Asturian Ministry of Health in Asturias-CSPA, the Public Health System of Asturias-SESPA, and the Foundation for the Promotion of Applied Scientific Research and Technology in Asturias-FICYT) organised the “train-the-trainers” training, i.e., the training of local healthcare staff that will be implementing the pilot actions across the different countries. Each local team is multidisciplinary, covering the roles of program coordinators, nutritionists/dietitians, GPs/endocrinologists, nurses, and, if applicable, coaches (or comparable figures).

During the whole task, VL supported CSPA, SESPA and FICYT for coaching individual countries. The training actions were continuously monitored for improvement. Satisfaction & opinions for evaluation and fine-tuning purposes were collected from healthcare participants. The assessment of the first cluster training served to correct any potential major bottlenecks and fine-tuning the next training. Healthcare professionals received a certificate upon completion of the training, which certified their capacities to train other health professionals in their country.

2.1. Organizational aspects of the training

The VL BP owner organized, with the support of the coordination team, three different rounds of trainings for the multidisciplinary team (MDT) in English as the common official language of the C4D JA. The sessions included the fundamental information, based on their own experience, required for the partners to acquire sufficient knowledge to reproduce the VL BP accordingly in each pilot implementation country/region.

The main objective of the sessions was the transfer of relevant information about the technical aspects of the BP (content, communication, organization) necessary to set up the pilots by their respective local teams.

The trainings were organized on 5-day online sessions of 7 hours duration each (9am to 4pm) extended over 8 weeks approximately. The 5 sessions were organized as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Time schedule of the training.

Following recommendations on VL, each cluster was composed of 4 or 5 countries. The 12 participant countries participating in the JA were divided into three cluster groups as detailed in Table 1. Three rounds of training were organised:

- Round 1. Finland, Italy, Slovenia, and Spain.
- Round 2. Belgium, Greece, Poland, and Portugal.
- Round 3. Bulgaria, Hungary, Malta, and Slovakia.

Two additional training sessions on medication reduction and the follow-up phase were added to the training as a common session for all the professionals trained in the program, as requested by some participants. Table 1 details the dates of the different sessions held.

Table 1. Clusters of countries and dates for the different sessions of the training.

	Start day 1	Start day 2	Return day after 2 weeks	Return day After 4 weeks	Return day after 8 weeks
Round 1 Slovenia Spain Italy Finland	10-05-2023	11-05-2023	24-05-2023	07-06-2023	28-06-2023
Round 2 Belgium Portugal Greece Poland	21-09-2023	22-09-2023	05-10-2023	19-10-2023	23-11-2023
Round 3 Slovakia Malta Bulgaria Hungary	28-09-2023	29-09-2023	12-10-2023	02-11-2023	30-11-2023
Webinar on medication reduction	07-12-2023				
Webinar on the follow-up phase (7-24 months).	08-01-2024				

The agendas of the different sessions are included in Annex I.

The training included transfer of knowledge by several experts' presentations. Additionally, participants acquired the knowledge by doing several exercises and conducting reflection assignments. The training lasted ca. 3 months.

2.2. Roles of the multidisciplinary team and number of professionals

An engaged and committed MDT is the key driving force for the successful transfer and implementation of the BP. Each pilot site identified personnel that would assume the core competencies described by the four roles established by the BP owner: **program coordinator, nutritionist, nurse/general practitioner (GP), and coach**. Additional information on the responsibility of the different roles identified can be found in the deliverable "D5.2. Country implementation plans."

Local teams, transferring and implementing the pilot actions received training to adopt specific competencies required for delivering the program, having in mind the existing local capacities and skills. When needed, healthcare staff could become trainers themselves, training and supporting further personnel that might be needed for the implementation of the BP at a local, regional or national level, i.e., professionals trained by VL would be “**replicators**” for training further staff that might be needed to implement the action.

Between 8 and 10 healthcare professionals per pilot country are expected to receive the train-the-trainers action. For those countries training a lower number of these, replication of trainings was envisioned.

2.3. Description of the intervention

The C4D JA is based on the transfer of the VL BP that aims to provide people with T2D with skills for incorporating healthy habits into their lifestyles in a dynamic way by experiencing and practicing the concepts delivered during the sessions. These habits are based on 4 pillars: nutrition, physical activity, sleep and relaxation (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Pillars of the C4D BP.

The program will be delivered along 12 months in 2 phases. The intensive phase (Phase I) consists in the creation of groups of people with T2D to participate in a self-management education and support intensive training for 6 months, and the aftercare or follow-up phase (Phase II) over the following 6 months aims to ensure that barriers are solved, and new habits get sustainable over time.

During the intensive phase, theoretical content and practical activities about the 4 pillars of the BP (Figure 2) will be transmitted. Activities and workshops related to this content may include physical exercises, cooking, etc. Due to the behavioral changes expected from the start of the program, the first pharmacological reduction of antidiabetic agents will be carried out before the start of the intervention. Other modifications in medication will be made during the course of the program based on the biometric levels of the participants. This will be performed under strict (and continuous) medical supervision.

A minimum number of 860 T2D participants are expected to be recruited by the different countries participating in the C4D JA. Additional details on the number of participants per country can be found in the deliverable “D5.2 Country implementation plans”.

Two rounds of 2-phase interventions (phase I-intensive and phase II-aftercare) with a 6-month duration each are planned: the first round (**round A**) of Phase I will include at least 340 patients from the 12 pilot Member States. This round will start on M12 (January 2024). The outcomes will be assessed after application of the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) methodology for needed corrections and fine-tuning. The second round (**round B**) will involve a higher number of patients (minimum of 520) and will start in October 2024. The consortium will not apply the PDSA approach to the Phase II of the second intervention round (round B), due to time constraints of the duration of the JA. Each group will be organized into groups of 20 people approximately on face-to-face or online formats.

a) Face-to-face refers to interventions that consist of group sessions over 12 months organized for the physical attendance of the participants. This modality will be supported by an online platform throughout the duration of the intervention and can include webinars and online sessions if that is deemed logistically appropriate for its correct development.

One overnight stay is recommended by BP owner in order to:

- Promote group bonding, through the joint acquisition of knowledge received and its practice.
- Focus. Participants are extracted from their own environment, responsibilities and situation at home.
- Assist monitoring. The stay would allow more control on following the program (less triggers in the program environment - as e.g., snacking).
- Safety. Participants would feel secure physically and emotionally, especially for patients with other medication than metformin.
- Unburden. The two starting days have a full schedule and are intensive. Participants may have to travel far to get to the location and sometimes it is not feasible to come and go two days in a row within the transport options.

b) Online refers to interventions that consist of a program carried out fully digital with no physical encounters, either at individual or group level. This modality will be also supported by an online platform throughout the duration of the intervention.

c) Hybrid refers to interventions that will develop both a face-to-face as well as online interventions with different groups of participants.

2.4. Description of the content of the VL trainings

VL provided in-depth information about the training content organized around the 4 pillars of the program (nutrition, physical activity, relaxation and sleep), including a deep understanding of the physiology sustaining them. Additionally, knowledge regarding all the relevant phases of the program including recruitment, registration, communications, data management and evaluation was shared.

The training sessions included a combination of medical, nutrition, behavior change and process parts. Presentations were interspersed with practice. Different learning forms are provided and there was time for discussion and digestion. Presentations were held by two medical staff, two nutritional therapists, two project coordinators and one behavior scientist/coach.

The main aspects discussed for each pillar are detailed below.

2.4.1. Physiology

The main aspects of the physiology of T2D were described on the first 2 days (Start days 1 and 2). These included:

- ✓ What is type 2 diabetes?
- ✓ Insulin resistance as the main problem
- ✓ Being overweight and insulin resistance are linked
- ✓ Different types of insulin resistance and their effects
- ✓ The link between insulin resistance and lifestyle

2.4.2. Pillars

2.4.2.1. Nutrition

The nutrition pillar was mainly described on the first and second days of the training (Start days 1 and 2). The information provided on these days was later reinforced in the remaining sessions.

The evidence-based nutritional approach developed by the BP is influenced by the Dutch diabetes federation guidelines, which, in turn, are in line with the most recently published consensus from the American Diabetes Association (ADA) and the European Association for the Study of Diabetes (EASD).

The aspects described during the course were:

- ✓ Why does not the standard dietary approach work?
- ✓ What are the nutritional principles of Reverse Diabetes2Now?
- ✓ What are the underlying pillars (in addition to reversing insulin resistance)?
- ✓ Reading food labels + supermarket safari
- ✓ How to adjust your favourite recipes - rebuilding recipes

Considering the absence of a clear international consensus surrounding nutritional recommendations for people with T2D, traditional recommendations focus on calorie restriction with no further advice in dietary composition. As the BP argues, this contributes to the lack of effectiveness we currently see in dietary strategies for people with T2D.¹⁻³

The **nutritional principles** of Reverse Diabetes2 Now are:

- Eat a diet with as much variety and as many unprocessed foods as possible
This principle was further justified by arguing that unprocessed foods contain the most nutrients and the least unnecessary additives, as well as leaving a person feeling fuller for longer.
- Plan-based food is the foundation of your diet
During the training the health benefits of eating plant-based foods were described. The high proportion of dietary fibre was highlighted, essential for the proper functioning of the digestive system and gut health.
- Beware of products that are high in sugar or starch

Caution with carbohydrates was recommended during the training to avoid large amounts of insulin circulating in the body and reduce the risk of cells becoming less sensitive (insulin resistance).

- Eat a maximum of three meals per day
The importance of allowing the body to go through fasting periods was also highlighted. This would allow space for fat burning for energy as circulating insulin levels remained low.
- Stop counting calories
This principle sustains the aim of achieving a long-time habit rather than following a restrictive diet for a period of time. It stands on the basis that an increased intake of vegetables (fibre rich) would help reaching satiety at a sensitive total amount of food intake, hence, calorie intake would be naturally restricted.
- Prioritize natural, unrefined fats
Another message transferred during the training was to increase the total intake of natural fresh unprocessed fats. VL argued that fats would help maintaining satiety. Evidence on the switch from fat to sugar as the main disruptor of metabolism was presented.
- Stay hydrated
The importance of hydration through unsweetened beverages was also considered by the BP principles during the training.
- Eat enough and savour your food
The importance of enjoying meals was the ultimate requirement of the nutrition principles in order to promote participants long-term adherence.

The **underlying pillars** (in addition to reversing insulin resistance) are:

- Stabilize blood glucose levels
- Reduce inflammation
- Optimize microbiota

Reading food labels, supermarket safari and adjustment of favourite recipes. For the first 4 weeks into the program, participants are expected to follow a set menu so that they can experience the impact of the suggested diet on their blood glucose levels and overall health and learn what a diet on these -principles looks like.

From then on, daily meals would respond to the participants' choice as long as the 8 nutritional principles are respected. Practical sessions, such as recipe building and tips on supermarket shopping, were added to the program of the trainings.

Additionally, a hands-on experiential activity was encouraged through the digital platform with the following suggestions:

15.05.2023	08:00	Yoghurt with berries and granola
16.05.2023	12:00	Tomato soup
17.05.2023	18:00	Tempeh with sesame seeds
18.05.2023	08:00	Chocolate mousse
19.05.2023	12:00	Beetroot salad
20.05.2023	18:00	Steak and mushrooms
21.05.2023	08:00	Warm apple quinoa
22.05.2023	12:00	Salad niçoise
23.05.2023	18:00	Grilled vegetables, parsnip chips and pan-fried salmon
24.05.2023	12:00	Stuffed sweet peppers

The respective recipes were shared with all the participants in the trainings.

2.4.2.2. Physical activity

Physical activity was the main pillar presented on day 3 (Return day 2 weeks) of the course. The training included information regarding the short- and long-term health benefits of regular practice of physical activity:

- ✓ Why is exercise so important in T2D
- ✓ What are the exercise principles of *Reverse Diabetes2 Now*

The **importance of exercise** in T2D was discussed in the short and long-term:

Shor-term:

- More stable blood glucose over the day
- Less energy dips and more energy in general

Long-term:

- Increase of muscle mass and decrease of fat mass
- An improvement in HbA1c

The **exercise principles** of *Reverse Diabetes2 Now* were presented as detailed below:

- Exercise around meals (ideally before the meal).

This is based on the premise that insulin levels are at its lowest and fat burning is increased.

- All types of movement counts

In order to try to overcome the idea that physical activity can only be practiced in a gym or other form of strenuous exercise, the program encourages participants to seek all possibilities of physical movement within their daily activities (i.e. taking the steps, getting off the bus slightly further from the destiny, etc.)

- Make it a daily habit

To attempt to make behaviours sustainable over time, routine can help turning them into habits

- Move as varied as possible, combining exercises that affect at different parts of the body and at different intensities.
- Do what suits you and enjoy it.

The presentation of these principles was accompanied by tips to participants during the training.

Following this philosophy, throughout all sessions different sorts of brief exercises of a few minutes duration were encouraged, such as boxing mimicking and aerobic exercises.

2.4.2.3. Relaxation

Relaxation was the main pillar presented on day 4 (Return day 4 weeks) of the course.

- ✓ Relationship between stress and type 2 diabetes
- ✓ Chronic stress is problematic
- ✓ Relaxation response
- ✓ Relaxation principles of *Reverse Diabetes2 Now*

Stress as a primal survival mechanism and its responses were described (fight, flight, freeze responses) as well as potential physical, mental, emotional and behavioural manifestations. The impact on health due to chronic stress was discussed, emphasizing the benefits of relaxation.

Practical tips such as relaxation tools were discussed:

- Breathing
- Positive thinking
- Gratitude
- Clearing the mind

The **relaxation principles** of *Reverse Diabetes2 Now* are:

- Be aware of what stress does to you
- Bring relaxation in your daily life
- Do what suits you

Short relaxation exercises were also included in all sessions.

2.2.2.4. Sleep

Sleep was the main pillar presented on day 5 (Return Day 8 weeks) of the course.

The information covered during the training for this pillar is summarized below.

- ✓ Why is sleep so important for our health
- ✓ The relationship between sleep and type 2 diabetes
- ✓ The relationship between relaxation and sleep
- ✓ The relationship between exercise and sleep
- ✓ How do you fall asleep
- ✓ Tips for good sleep habits
- ✓ The sleep principles of *Reverse Diabetes2 Now*

Different aspects for falling asleep were covered during the training:

- Adenosine build up
- 24-h clock (circadian rhythm)
- Tips for good sleeping habits:
 - Caffeine intake
 - Body temperature/ Room temperature
 - Reduced stimuli
 - Daily schedule
 - Relaxation
 - Screen time
 - Circadian rhythm

The **sleep principles** of the BP are:

- It is about quality more than quantity
- Develop your sleep routine
- Enjoy sleep

Meetups in between and after the training days were offered as support, based on the needs of the group or specific roles.

2.5. Preparatory actions and materials

2.5.1. Preparatory actions

VL reported the following set up and preparation of the training activities before the first round of “Training-the- trainers”:

- ✓ Planning of the training days for the first round and planning of individual sessions with the training team.
- ✓ Holding development sessions with team of experts to develop the training.
- ✓ Setup of the program, learning goals, handbook and time schedule for the online training.
- ✓ Development of materials for the training including presentations, assessments, cases and, test materials.

Actions for content development for the training were reported by VL too. In particular, the following activities were developed:

- ✓ Training program for each day.
- ✓ Detailed schedule with content of training hours.
- ✓ Diagrams and visuals for training.
- ✓ Overview agenda and invitation so that participants of training know what to expect.
- ✓ Creating content community.
- ✓ Different work cases of patients and situations (per discipline/per role).
- ✓ Learning objectives per training section.
- ✓ Assessments and certification method.
- ✓ Assignments, polls and exam.

2.5.2. Materials

2.5.2.1. Presentations

The materials used for the delivery of the content included presentations for each of the sessions as detailed below.

ROUND 1 (R1)

- ✓ Presentation Start day 1
- ✓ Presentation Start day 2
- ✓ Presentation Return day- 2 weeks
- ✓ Presentation Return day - 4 weeks
- ✓ Presentation Return day - 8 weeks

ROUNDS 2 & 3 (R2 and R3)

- ✓ Diabetes physiology- EU (training- R3)
- ✓ Nutrition-ii-practice-EU (training-R2 and R1)
- ✓ Nutrition-i-theory- EU (training-R2 and R1)
- ✓ Presentation-startday (R3)
- ✓ Presentation-startday-2 (R3)
- ✓ Presentation-rd-2-weeks (R3)
- ✓ Presentation-rd-4-weeks (R3)

OTHER MATERIAL & PRESENTATIONS MEETUP

- ✓ Reports & articles:
 - 2018 Pot- Nutrition and lifestyle intervention in type 2 diabetes
 - 2020 Pot- Lifestyle medicine for type 2 diabetes (Reverse Diabetes2 Now)
 - A Consensus Report by the American Diabetes Association (ADA) and the European Association for the Study of Diabetes (EASD)
- ✓ Financial impact of Reverse Diabetes2 Now
- ✓ Meet up- medication reduction higher complex patients
- ✓ Pilot implementation plan (R3)

A

complete description of the materials used for the delivery of the training is available in Annex II. The materials were organized into different chapters and colors as shown below.

- ✓ Aftercare phase
- ✓ Chapter 1- BLUE- Recruitment & Registration of participants (inclusion protocol, roles, patient flow, recruitment of participants, registration forms, etc.)
- ✓ Chapter 2- PINK- Content during program (objectives, coaching, nutrition, participants book, nutrition, movement, relaxation)
- ✓ Chapter 3- YELLOW- Communication (communication with lead practitioner, communication among participants, communication tasks of program coordinator)
- ✓ Chapter 4- RED- Medical (adapting medication, instructions, medical safety)
- ✓ Chapter 5- GREEN- General (background, literature, ICT systems, financial impact, etc.)
- ✓ Chapter 6- BROWN- Data & Evaluation
- ✓ Overview & introduction materials

An example of the materials provided by VL can be found in Annex III.

Co-funded by
the European Union

The project CARE4DIABETES has received funding from the European Commission under GA No 101082427.

2.5.2.2. Digital platform

The VL digital platform (<https://mijnvoedingleeft.nl/en>) was presented during the training sessions. The platform contains different sections including dashboard, community and library sections. The VL digital platform acts as an “all-in-one” platform which addresses the management of:

- **clinical data**, including participants’ personal and sensible data. This shall fully comply with the GDPR as for data security, and privacy.
- **participants’ self-reported data** (monitoring functions). This is used by participants and the team to track changes along the program, and shall rely on secure questionnaires and tools. Example of data collected are periodic glucose measurements and weight and circumference measurements.
- activities, resources, and community-based interactions among the participants and with the multidisciplinary team’s members for **social interaction**. Social interaction features are meant to facilitate the interaction among participants and between participants and the team, the participants’ consultation of helpful contents, the assignment of calendar activities or the delivery of webinars. Supervision is needed by the team to avoid the dissemination of unsuitable or even risky contents and messages; data security and privacy shall be guaranteed as well; participants shall always be informed on the level of possible dissemination of their data and shall deliver their signed consent.

Each country participating in the pilots within C4D JA will adopt a digital solution to deliver the program of the pilot studies. Within the C4D JA, and according to each implementer country’s resources and context, the above three main groups of functions (i.e., clinical data management, self-reported data monitoring, and social interaction) can be delivered either by means of an “all-in-one” dedicated platform or via separated, ad-hoc or adapted from existing, digital solutions. The management of clinical data can either be performed within a regional/national health information system, or implemented via a dedicated platform which shall however act through secure authentication procedures.

Most of the partners will use the Moddle digital platform designed by the Italian National Institute of Health (ISS) whereas other partners will use their own. Additional details on the requirements and details of the platform can be found in deliverable “D.3. *Guidelines for online systems and platforms*”.

2.6. Completion of the trainings and evaluation

The first round of the training was prepared separately from the second and third rounds, that were prepared simultaneously after an internal assessment done over the first round. The second and third round of the trainings were prepared simultaneously and VL described their preparatory activities:

- ✓ Evaluation of the first round.
- ✓ Reviewing evaluation form participants and reviewing trainee needs.
- ✓ Total team evaluation session after round 1 of the training.
- ✓ Adjustments in training content, presentations and timetable of the training days for further development for round 2.
- ✓ Final planning the training days for the second and third round, team division and schedule online meetings, preparation sessions with the training team.

The VL team provided a certificate upon successful completion of the training, based on the following 3 criteria: successfully completing an exam (theoretical), presenting the own implementation plan and attending at least 4 of the 5 training days (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Model of certificate issued to the trainers that successfully completed the training.

The internal assessment of the first round of training by VL served to correct any potential bottleneck and fine tune the next trainings. VL evaluated the first round of training with the whole team, taking into consideration participants feedback and the report from THL evaluation questionnaires and taking actions in order to prepare the next second and third rounds of training, planning the training days and their respective sessions with the correspondent additions in schedule and script.

One additional evaluation was also performed in the framework of the C4D project. THL performed an evaluation of the training activities by using questionnaires that collected the feedback from the participants. The items and questions included in this questionnaire were:

- A.** The previous knowledge of the professionals:
 - Their own knowledge on the role of lifestyles in T2D management before the training (from 1-extremely poor- to 10-extremely good-)
 - Their competence in implementing lifestyle guidance for people with T2D before the training (1-10)
- B.** The satisfaction of the training:
 - The training day was well-organized (from 1-totally disagree- to 5-totally agree-)
 - I got enough information before the training day (1-5)
 - The objectives of the day were clear (1-5)
 - The agenda was interesting and useful for me (1-5)
 - The content of presentations included new information for me (1-5)
 - Opportunities to participate and contribute to the training (1-5)
 - Opportunities for learning and exchange of experiences (1-5)
 - Enough time was allocated for discussion (1-5)
 - The technical management of the online venue worked well (1-5)
 - Attending the training was good use of my time (1-5)
 - I got relevant information to implement the R2D model in our pilot (1-5)
 - The homework/prereading material was useful (if relevant) (1-5)
 - The exercises during training day were useful (1-5)
 - I learnt new information which is relevant for the implementation (1-5)
- C.** What were the main benefits for you and your team from this training day?
- D.** How would you rate the day overall (1-10)
- E.** How would you rate:
 - your knowledge on the role of lifestyles in T2D management after the training (1-10)
 - your competence in implementing lifestyle guidance for people with T2D after the training (1-10)

- the relevance of Voeding Lefst materials for implementing lifestyle guidance for people with T2D (1-10)
- F.** Do you have any further comments or suggestions?

The questionnaire was circulated after the completion of each session of the training.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Number of healthcare professionals trained and roles

The number of trainers registered and qualified for each country are shown in Table 2. A total number of 90 professionals from the 12 countries involved in the pilots attended the VL training. These covered the identified roles by VL including coordinators, nutritionists/dietitians, GPs/endocrinologists, nurses, and coaches. Also, IT developers and additional staff (observers) attended the training.

In total, 70 participants received a certificate upon successful completion of the training, based on the 3 criteria for evaluation (i.e., successfully completing an exam (theoretical), presenting their implementation plan and attending at least 4 of the 5 training days).

Table 2 – Number of registered and qualified trainers for the different rounds

Round	Country	Roles and total number of attendees	Number of professionals certified
Round 1	Spain	2 coordinators, 2 coaches, 2 GP, 3 nurse/dietician, 1 observer Total: 10	9
	Finland	3 coordinators, 1 coach, 1 dietician, 1 nurse Total: 6	6
	Slovenia	2 coordinators, 1coach, 1 nurse, 1 diabetologist, 1 dietician and 2 observers Total: 8	4
	Italy	2 IT developers 3 nurses/coaches 2 medical doctor, diabetologist Total: 7	6
Round 2	Poland	2 coordinators, 1 dietician, 1 diabetologist, 1 GP, 2 nurses, 1 coach, 2 observers-coordinators Total: 10	7
	Portugal	3 coordinators, 2 coaches, 2 nurses, 2 medical doctors, 1 dietician Total: 10	10
	Belgium	2 coordinators, 1 nurse Total: 3	3

	Greece	2 coordinators, 4 medical doctors, 1 dietician 3 nurse/ diabetes nurse Total: 10	4
Round 3	Hungary	1 coordinator, 1 coach, 1 dietician, 1 nurse Total: 4	4
	Slovakia	1 coordinator, 1 GP, 1 nurse, 1 nutritionist, 1 coach, 3 observers (MoH experts) Total: 8	5
	Malta	1 coordinator, 1 medical doctor, 1 nurse, 1 dietician, 2 coaches, 1 observer (senior expert) Total: 7	7
	Bulgaria	1 coordinator, 1 medical doctor, 1 nurse, 1 dietician, 1 coach (kinesitherapist), 2 observers Total: 7	5
Total	All countries	90	70

Replication of trainings

The qualified trainers extended the trainings to other local settings in some of the countries participating in the JA. This is the case of Belgium, Portugal and Spain where the professionals trained by VL further trained (or are in the process of training) additional healthcare professionals. The results of the replication of trainings are shown in Table 3.

Twelve, 6 and 25 additional healthcare professionals have been successfully trained in Belgium, Italy and Spain by certified trainers of VL, respectively. The replication of trainings is currently ongoing in the case of Portugal and data is not available yet.

Table 3 – Number of registered and qualified trainers for the replication trainings.

Round	Country	Registered	Number of professionals qualified and roles
Replication	Belgium	12	3 coordinators, 3 nurses, 4 dieticians, 2 coaches (1 psychologist and 1 nurse) Total: 12
	Italy	6	3 diabetologists, 1 dietician, 1 coach, 1 coordinator Total: 6
	Spain	25	3 coordinators, 5 medical doctors, 7 nurses, 7 dietitians, 3 coaches Total: 25

	Portugal	N/A (training is ongoing and will finish early January)	N/A
--	----------	---	-----

N/A: non available

In addition, additional informal trainings (non-structured nor certified trainings) were held in Slovenia and Finland. Three professionals (1 nurse, 1 coach and 1 program coordinator) were trained on new education materials in Slovenia and two professionals (1 nurse and one coach) were trained in Finland.

3.2. Evaluation of the trainings

3.2.1. Evaluation performed by VL

During the development of the first-round training sessions VL, the feedback collected by VL from participants were incorporated in the following rounds. This was valuable information taken into consideration for the second and third round preparatory actions. Most of the comments dealt with including more "how-tos" and practical examples implemented in training and coaching the participants in behaviour change.

The suggestions received by the participants of the first round and the list of actions and changes made in rounds 2 and 3 are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4 – List of actions after round 1 and further development for round 2 and 3.

Comment/suggestion	Explanation
General More key messages & clearer distinction added to clarify when shared information was for the participant and when for the professional.	All program content and information shared in the presentations was reviewed. In the feedback provided by the participants of the training there were some participants who mentioned the need for a clearer distinction between information provided for them as professionals and information that should be shared with participants. Therefore, all presentations have been checked and adjusted so that for the whole training, the team makes sure all participants know what is for the participants and what information is important for them to know as a professional, when delivering the program.
Process & operation More attention is paid to the process & operation of pilot implementation.	The evaluation showed that some participants would like to have a more complete view of the RD2N model and the process and operational effort needed to start the pilot. Therefore, during the start days the full view of the RD2N model in the first six months is explained and more detail was provided on the process & operation requirements for starting the pilot.
Process & operation Additional information about the aftercare (follow-up phase) is added.	Participating countries in the first round asked for additional information about the follow-up phase after 6 months. In the first round VL provided limited information about the follow-up phase after 6 months (the aftercare). VL added more information to the training day after 4 weeks about the aftercare phase.

<p>Coaching Science behind the models and exercises related to behaviour change</p>	<p>Feedback provided on the coaching part suggested that participants were interested in more information on "how-tos" and practical examples of what Reverse Diabetes2 Now do with participants and how to manage participant behaviour change during the program.</p> <p>The coaching section is built up in 4 parts. First, the science behind the program is explained (scientific models and theories about behaviour change), the most important lessons we've learned are shared, then an overview is given and explained of coaching themes and how the coach sessions are built up. In addition, different tools with cases in coaching and group coaching are practised and here additional information was provided.</p>
<p>Medical More case-based learning on medication reduction in the longer run</p>	<p>Extra room for discussion was encouraged with more case-based learning on reducing medication for rounds 2 and 3. On the return day after 4 weeks the first round teams practised with cases on short term medication reduction in the program. For rounds 2 and 3 further 'real life' cases were added to practise with medication in the longer run of the program as well. A further session on reducing insulin has been developed and provided in December to all countries including participants on insulin in their pilots.</p>

3.2.2. Evaluation performed in the framework of the C4D project

For round 1, 25 participants received the certificate upon successful completion of the training, based on the 3 criteria for evaluation (i.e., successfully completing an exam, presenting their implementation plan and attending at least 4 of the 5 training days). For rounds 2 and 3 24 and 21 participants were certified, respectively.

The main results from the evaluation analysis are discussed below.

- **Previous knowledge of the professionals.**

- The own knowledge on the role of lifestyles in T2D management before the training scored an average value of 7.4 (n=18), 7.3 (n=14) and 7.3 (n=13) for rounds 1, 2 and 3, respectively.
- Their competence in implementing lifestyle guidance for people with T2D before the training scored an average value of 6.8 (n=18), 6.9 (n=14) and 6.3 (n=13) for rounds 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

- **The satisfaction of the training.**

The results show a positive satisfaction with the trainings. The different items considered for measuring the degree of satisfaction scored an increasing average value of 4.2, 4.4 and 4.6 over 5 for rounds 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

The scores ranged between 3.9 for the novelty in the information included in the presentations and 4.7-4.8 over 5 for the technical management of the online venue and the

organisation of the training. Also, high scores of 4.5-4.7 were obtained for the opportunities provided to participate and contribute to the training, the opportunities for learning and exchanging experiences, the usefulness of the agenda, the exercises during the training day and the time allocated for discussion. It is worth noting that the percentage of answers with a score of 5 increased from 48% for the first round, to 50 and 69% for the second and third round, respectively.

- **Benefits for the trainers and their team.** The main benefits highlighted were:
 - **Content of the training.** The main points highlighted as positive for the outcomes of the training were: the new information received so that participants can make an introductory training for the patients which is both interesting and motivating making use of the importance of small choices, the real cases used, the new knowledge about nutrition, group coaching (including practical aspects which were very nice and effective) and good habits in life, getting more information and practical information about the R2D program, to learn the "behind scenes" of the program - why it has been so successful, practical aspects and better understand the materials, presentation of useful case examples for inclusion and exclusion, exercise and motivation approach are shown in a different way to regular once and is very useful, learn more about the pathology and physiology (T2D) (e.g. modern physiological concept concepts like inflammation, microbiota, ...) and management of the medication, prevention and risk factors, and learn a bit how to approach a scientific explanation in basic and understandable ways so as to use it with participants/patients and got very interesting tips both as new knowledge/understanding and from an experiential point of view, more awareness of the impact of the psychological part/stress in health, the good contents about the motivation, stress and stress management/relaxation (e.g. box breathing)/sleep, learning about hormonal changes during sleep and sleep cycle, and knowledge of basic tips on how to help participants to start thinking differently.
 - **General organisational aspects.** Positive comments on the organisation of the training were received for the following aspects:
 - Motivation, active discussion was facilitated in small groups, it has been a very enriching training.
 - The materials used for the delivery of the training were very eye-opening, relevant, and organized. The explanatory slides were an excellent complement to the classes which reinforced key ideas from days 1 and 2 or previous introduced ideas.

- Sharing with professional colleagues from different countries and specializations was very valuable. The training allowed to reflect on the cultural differences that might hinder the own pilot studies, and to learn how other countries will implement the pilot and gather ideas for planning own pilots/placing different dietary patterns.
 - The increase in knowledge and skillset, as well as the practical aspects of the course were extremely beneficial.
- **Rate of the sessions.** The rate of the sessions was higher than 8.0 over 10 for all sessions. An average increasing rate of 8.3 (n=63), 8.4 (n=47) and 9.1 (n=50) was obtained for rounds 1, 2 and 3, respectively.
 - **Knowledge and competence of the professionals after the training.** Data gathered for this topic show that:
 - The knowledge of the professionals on the role of lifestyles in T2D management after the training scored an average value of 8.7 (n=17), 7.8 (n=11) and 9.2 (n=10) over 10 for rounds 1, 2 and 3, respectively.
 - The competence of professionals in implementing lifestyle guidance for people with T2D after the training scored an average value of 8.6 (n=17), 7.5 (n=11) and 8.9 (n=10) for rounds 1, 2 and 3, respectively.
 - The relevance of VL materials for implementing lifestyle guidance for people with T2D scored 8.2 (n=17), 7.5 (n=11) and 9.2 (n=10) for rounds 1, 2 and 3, respectively.
 - **Comments and/or suggestions**
 - **Content of the training**
 - Strengths. The positive comments received were: motivation part was good, the content was full of knowledge and very useful, some topics were new and interesting (like information on recruitment and registration or the pillars of physical exercise).
 - Weaknesses. These were mainly detected for round 1. The comments received were: the scientific references behind the research and meta-analyses are missing; it would be more convincing to talk more about physiological background e.g. glycogenesis, how manage high insulin level and hungry, including case discussions for the mental part; it is still quite unclear which parts of the training are part of the training of trainers and

which parts are fully adaptable for the participants of the program; it would be nice to get a better idea of the coaching and the behaviour change; now the content for trainers are mixed with the content for participants, focussing more on participants; it would be positive to know how to train the participants rather than following the RD2N model; too much medical physiopathology, it would be better to learn how we can teach the patient, working with insulin resistance; including situation regarding how to deal with unmotivated participants; adding more exercises and information on coaching, how to vary these according to audience, what to do to increase motivation, what exercise snacks etc VL uses and how often, etc.; some practical examples were overlooked in the training (e.g. physical exercises foreseen for the participant with T2D, ...); the indications provided (with the exception of the notions on nutrition) should have been more practical; there was unfortunately quite little information of how the model has been implemented, mainly about the lifestyle education that VL has been giving in Netherlands; it is confusing to get information that contradicts international and national guidelines; regarding coaching, more specific and practical information is necessary in order to know what kind of activities to do in the pilot; better clarification about the protocols.

General organisational aspects

- Strengths. The strengths pointed included: very professional people and excellent communicators; the training days have good organization; good knowledge, skills and application with such clear presentations; eye-opening and well-organized course.
- Weaknesses. Comments to better improve the training were: it would have been better if the training was delivered before, when we actually had to work on the implementation plan as part of the WP; consideration a differentiated range of information on individual topics for doctors, nurses, psychologists, dietitians; the agenda was not very clear (e.g. lunch break, etc), having the schedule in advance; on the final day feedback on the contributions sent and a more open space for general discussion would have been appreciated; too many hours per day for each session; more advice on how to present the info for participants and how to arrange the sessions; last session included new knowledge that was part of the final test; maybe reducing time on breakout rooms or adding more material for discussion; the level of English of attendees should be adequate; more time for exercises.

In summary, the results from the evaluation analysis indicate increasing rates of satisfaction with the delivery of the program for the different rounds of training.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The C4D JA supports twelve Member States (Belgium, Bulgaria, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia and Spain) in reducing the burden of type 2 diabetes (T2D) through effective lifestyle treatment programs.

These deliverable details the actions performed by the BP owner (VL) for transferring the content of the BP to the professionals in the countries implementing the program in C4D Joint Action, including the replication actions. It describes the organization, development of the “Train-the-trainers” training of local healthcare professionals and the evaluation of the different clusters training. The intended audience are all members of the C4D consortium (competent authorities and affiliated entities), especially the WP leaders, C4D teams from implementing countries, stakeholders involved in the pilot implementation and/or dissemination and scale-up of the VL BP, and other entities interested in gaining knowledge of the BP to be implemented in their settings.

The methodology was developed by the VL team, based on their experience along the years of implementation in the Netherlands.

All the countries in the Joint Action took part in the training courses, which were divided per clusters of countries with 4 countries *per* cluster and 3 rounds of trainings organised between 10 May 2023 and 30 November 2023.

A total number of 70 professionals were successfully trained and certified as trainers by VL, and until now three countries (Belgium, Italy and Spain) replicated the trainings to train additional 43 professionals. The replication process is currently ongoing in Portugal.

In order to ensure the impact and long-term sustainability of the program, further cascade trainings may be carried out in some of the countries.

The training was designed to adjust and feed the first and subsequent rounds for improvement and increased outcomes. The results from the evaluation analysis are presented and discussed as part of this deliverable and show increasing rates of satisfaction with the delivery of the program for the different rounds of training organised over time. Key outcomes will also feed interim evaluation report in WP3. The identified weaknesses and strengths of the training delivered by VL will serve to better improve further trainings in the future and/or assist the design of the transfer of the BP in other settings.

5. REFERENCES

1. Pot GK, Battjes-Fries MC, Patijn ON, Pijl H, Witkamp RF, de Visser M, van der Zijl N, de Vries M, Voshol PJ. Nutrition and lifestyle intervention in type 2 diabetes: pilot study in the Netherlands showing improved glucose control and reduction in glucose lowering medication. *BMJ Nutr Prev Health*. 2019 May 14;2(1):43-50. doi: 10.1136/bmjnp-2018-000012. PMID: 33235957; PMCID: PMC7678479.
2. Pot GK, Battjes-Fries MC, Patijn ON, van der Zijl N, Pijl H, Voshol P. Lifestyle medicine for type 2 diabetes: practice-based evidence for long-term efficacy of a multicomponent lifestyle intervention (Reverse Diabetes2 Now). *BMJ Nutr Prev Health*. 2020 Aug 18;3(2):188-195. doi: 10.1136/bmjnp-2020-000081. PMID: 33521528; PMCID: PMC7841830.
3. Murdoch C, Unwin D, Cavan D, Cucuzzella M, Patel M. Adapting diabetes medication for low carbohydrate management of type 2 diabetes: a practical guide. *Br J Gen Pract*. 2019 Jul;69(684):360-361. doi: 10.3399/bjgp19X704525. PMID: 31249097; PMCID: PMC6592353.

6. ANNEXES

ANNEX 1. AGENDAS OF THE VL TRAININGS

ROUND 1- Finland, Italy, Slovenia, and Spain.

Session	Date + Time	Topics	Experts delivering the program
Start day 1	05 - 10 - 2023 09.00 - 15.00 h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General • Process • Nutrition • Behavior change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Moderator + Coach</i> • Medical • Project leads • Nutrition + pillars/Nutrition + pillars
Start day 2	05 - 11 - 2023 09.00 - 15.00 h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General • Process • Pathophysiology • Nutrition • Behavior change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Moderator + Coach</i> • Medical/Pathophysiology • Project leads • Nutrition + pillars/Nutrition + pillars
Return day after 2 weeks	05 - 24 - 2023 09.00 - 15.00 H	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General • Process • Medical • Exercise • Behavior change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Moderator + Coach</i> • Medical/Pathophysiology • Project leads • Nutrition + pillars/Nutrition + pillars
Returnday after 4 weeks	06 - 07 - 2023 09.00 - 15.00 h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General • Process • Medical • Relaxation • Behavior change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Moderator + Coach</i> • Medical • Project lead/Project lead • Nutrition + pillars/Nutrition + pillars
Returnday after 8 weeks	06 - 28 - 2023 09.00 - 15.00 h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General • Sleep • Implementation plan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Moderator + Coach</i> • Medical • Project lead/Project lead • Nutrition + pillars/Nutrition + pillars

Start day 1:

08.15-08.45	Team pre-talk <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slide 1 in welcome screen 	Team
08.45-09.00	Welcoming & helping participants in ZOOM	Team

09.00-09 .45	Welcome <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meet the VL team • Get to know Voeding Leeft 1 slide • Results 1 slide • Get to know each other <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ 2 poll questions ◦ What makes you happy - answers in chat 	Moderator + Coach Medical Moderator + Coach
09.45 - 09.55	Relaxation exercise	Moderator + Coach
09.55 - 10.20	Explanation process <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expectations • Information • Materials 	Project lead/Project lead
10.20-10.30	Break	
10.30 - 11.15	Nutrition part 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • basic pathophysiology DM2 	Nutrition + pillars
11.15 - 11.20	Snaxercise	Project lead
11.20 - 12.30	Nutrition part 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poll questions • Interactive moments 	Nutrition + pillars
12.30 - 13.15	Lunch break <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • depends on the amount of questions 	
13.15 - 14.00	Nutrition part 3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blood glucose • Principles 	Nutrition + pillars
14.00 - 14.05	Break	
14.05 - 14.50	Behavior change <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Theory 	Moderator + Coach

Start day 2:

08.30 - 09.00	Team pre-talk	Team
09.00 - 09.15	Opening <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Question in chat about yesterday • Basic moderations 	Moderator
09.15 - 09.20	Relaxation exercise	Moderator + Coach
09.20 - 10.00	Process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information about the program 	Project lead/Project lead
10.00 - 10.45	Pathophysiology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repetition of basics (day 1) • In depth information part 1 	Pathophysiology + Medical
10.45 - 11.00	Break + snaxercise	Project lead
11.00 - 12.00	Pathophysiology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In depth information part 2 	Pathophysiology + Medical

12.00 - 12.45	Lunch break	
12.45 - 13.45	Nutrition part 4 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reading labels + supermarket safari • Rebuilding recipes • Break out rooms • National dish 	Nutrition + pillars
13.45 - 13.50	Break	
13.50 - 14.50	Behavior change <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cases 	Moderator + Coach
14.50 - 15.00	Closing	Moderator

Return day after 2 weeks:

08.30 - 09.00	Team pre-talk	Team
09.00 - 09.15	Welcome & opening <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic moderations 	Moderator
09.15 - 09.20	Relaxation exercise	Moderator + Coach
09.20 - 10.00	Process <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you need to begin 	Project lead/Project lead
10.00 - 10.45	Medical part 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusion process • Break out rooms 	Medical
10.45 - 11.00	Break + snaxercise	Project lead
11.00 - 12.15	Medical part 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cases • Break out rooms 	Pathophysiology + Medical
12.15 - 13.00	Lunch break	
13.00 - 14.00	Pillar Exercise	Nutrition + pillars
14.00 - 14.05	Break	
14.05 - 14.50	Coach subjects <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examples 	Moderator + Coach
14.50 - 15.00	Closing	Moderator

Return day after 4 weeks:

08.15 - 09.00	Team pre-talk	Team
09.00 - 09.15	Welcome & opening <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic moderations 	Moderator
09.15 - 09.20	Relaxation exercise	Moderator + Coach
09.20 - 10.00	Process <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chapter Yellow • Chapter Brown 	Project lead/Project lead
10.00 - 10.45	Medical part 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reducing medication 	Medical

10.45 - 11.00	Break + snaxercise	Project lead
11.00 - 12.00	Medical part 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cases • Break out rooms 	Medical
12.00 - 12.45	Lunch break	
12.45 - 13.45	Pillar Relaxation	Nutrition + pillars
13.45 - 13.50	Break	
13.50 - 14.05	Explanation “action implementation plan”	Project lead/Project lead
14.05 - 14.50	Behavior change <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cases 	Moderator + Coach
14.50 - 15.00	Closing	Moderator

Return day after 8 weeks:

08.30 - 09.00	Team pre-talk	Team
09.00 - 09.25	Welcome & opening <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic moderations 	Moderator
09.25 - 09.30	Relaxation exercise	Moderator + Coach
09.30 - 10.30	Pillar Sleep	Nutrition + pillars
10.30 - 10.45	Break + snaxercise	Project lead
10.45-11.45	Exam	
11.45-12.00	Introduction and explanation presentations action plan	
12.00 - 13.00	Lunch break	
13.00 - 13.45	Presentations teams part 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feedback loop • Final questions 	Team
14.00 - 14.45	Presentations teams part 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feedback loop • Final questions 	Team
14.45 - 15.00	Closing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Certification 	Team

ROUND 2- Belgium, Greece, Poland, and Portugal

Session	Date + Time	Topics	Experts delivering the program
Startday 1	Sept 21 - 2023 09.00 - 15.00 h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General • Process • Nutrition • Behavior change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderator + Coach • Medical • Project lead/Project lead • Nutrition + pillars/Nutrition + pillars
Startday 2	Sept 22 - 2023 09.00 - 15.00 h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General • Process • Pathophysiology • Nutrition • Behavior change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderator + Coach • Medical/Pathophysiology • Project lead/Project lead • Nutrition + pillars/Nutrition + pillars
Returnday after 2 weeks	Oct 5 - 2023 09.00 - 15.00 h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General • Process • Medical • Exercise • Behavior change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderator + Coach • Medical/Pathophysiology? • Project lead/Project lead • Nutrition + pillars/Nutrition + pillars
Returnday after 4 weeks	Oct 19 - 2023 09.00 - 15.00 h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General • Process • Medical • Relaxation • Behavior change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderator + Coach • Medical • Project lead/Project lead • Nutrition + pillars/Nutrition + pillars
Returnday after 8 weeks	Nov 23 - 2023 09.00 - 15.00 h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General • Sleep • Exam • Implementation plan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderator + Coach • Medical • Project lead/Project lead • Nutrition + pillars/Nutrition + pillars

Start day 1

08.15-08.45	Team pre-talk	Team
08.45-09.00	Welcoming participants in ZOOM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome slide in screen 	Team
09.00-09.30	Welcome <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meet the VL team (introducing team members) Get to know Voeding Leeft - <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Background VL Why are we here today with each other? Where do we come from? Timeline Get to know the program Get to know each other <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Break out rooms - 6 min - (get to know each other in small groups by discipline). Today's & program tomorrow Relaxation exercise 	Project lead Moderator + Coach & Medical Project lead Moderator + Coach
09.30 - 09.45	Explanation process training <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expectations 	Project lead
09.45 - 09.50	Moderation - Snaxercise	Project lead
09.50 - 10.35	Pathophysiology DM2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (part 1) Interactive moments 	Pathophysiology & Medical
10.35-10.45	Break (big timer)	Project lead
10.45 - 11.30	Pathophysiology DM2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (part 2) Interactive moments 	Pathophysiology & Medical
11.30 - 11.40	Moderation	Project lead
11.45 - till lunch break	Q&A	Pathophysiology & Medical
12.30 - 13.15	Lunch break <ul style="list-style-type: none"> depends on the amount of questions 	Project lead
13.15 - 13.50	Nutrition	Nutrition + pillars
13.50 - 13.55	Snaxercise	Project lead
13.50 - 14.20	Nutrition	Nutrition + pillars
14.20 - 14.25	Break (big timer)	Project lead
14.25 - 14.55	Nutrition	Nutrition + pillars
14.55- 15.00	Closing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planning next day 	Project lead & Project lead

Start day 2

08.30 - 09.00	Team pre-talk	Team
09.00 - 09.15	Opening <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Question in chat about yesterday • Basic moderations 	Project lead
09.15 - 09.20	Relaxation exercise	Project lead
09.20 - 10.00	Process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction materials • Introduction pilot implementation plan • Introduction program RD2N • community 	Project lead
10.00 - 10.45	Nutrition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repetition of basics (day 1) • In depth information part 1 	Nutrition + pillars
10.45 - 11.00	Break + snaxercise	Project lead
11.00 - 12.00	Nutrition part 4 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reading labels + supermarket safari • Rebuilding recipes • Break out rooms • National dish 	Nutrition + pillars
12.00 - 12.45	Lunch break	Project lead
12.45 - 13.45	Behavior change <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basics & theory 	Moderator + Coach
13.45 - 13.50	Break	
13.50 - 14.50	Behavior change <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cases & break out rooms 	Moderator + Coach
14.50 - 15.00	Closing	Moderator

Return day after 2 weeks

08.30 - 09.00	Team pre-talk	Team
09.00 - 09.10	Welcome & opening	Project lead
09.10 - 09.15	Relaxation exercise	Moderator + Coach
09.15 - 10.30	Behavior change	Moderator + Coach
10.30 - 10:40	Break	Project lead
10.40 - 12.00	Pillar Exercise <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Snaxercise in between 	Nutrition + pillars
12.00 - 13.00	Lunch break	Project lead
13.00 - 13.15	Process <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you need to begin 	Project lead & Project lead
13.15 - 14.00	Medical part 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusion process • Break out rooms 	Medical & Project lead
13.45 - 14.00	Break & snaxercise	Project lead

14.00 - 14.50	Medical part 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cases • Break out rooms • Q&A 	Medical & Project lead
14.50 - 15.00	Closing	Project lead

Return day after 4 weeks

08.30 - 09.00	Team pre-talk	Team
09.00 - 09.10	Welcome & opening <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic moderations 	Project lead
09.10 - 09.15	Relaxation exercise	Project lead
09.15 - 10.00	Process <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • communication • data & evaluation • after care phase • action implementation plan 	Project lead
10.00 - 10.45	Medical part 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reducing medication 	Medical
10.45 - 11.00	Break	Project lead
11.00 - 12.00	Medical part 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cases • Break out rooms • Summary for each country 	Medical
12.00 - 13.00	Lunch break	
13.00 - 13.00	Pillar Relaxation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • part 1 	Nutrition + pillars
13.30 - 13.35	Snaxercise	Project lead
13.35 - 14.05	Pillar Relaxation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • part 2 	Nutrition + pillars
14.05 - 14.55	Behavior change <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cases 	Moderator + Coach
14.55 - 15.00	Closing	Project lead

Return day after 8 weeks

08.30 - 09.00	Team pre-talk	Team
09.00 - 09.05	Welcome & opening • Basic moderations	Project lead
09.05 - 09.15	Relaxation exercise	Moderator + Coach
09.15 - 10.30	Pillar Sleep	Nutrition + pillars
10.30 - 10.45	Break + snaxercise	Project lead
10.45-11.30	Exam	Nutrition + pillars & Project lead
11.30-11.45	Results & introduction presentations action plan afternoon	Project lead
11.45 - 12.45	Lunch break	
12.45 - 13.15	Country 1 • 10 minutes presentation • 10 minutes break out rooms countries separated • 10 minutes asking questions & grades	team
13.15 - 13.45	Country 2 • 10 minutes presentation • 10 minutes break out rooms countries separated • 10 minutes asking questions & grades	team
13.45 - 14.15	Country 3 • 10 minutes presentation • 10 minutes break out rooms countries separated • 10 minutes asking questions & grades	team

ROUND 3- Bulgaria, Hungary, Malta, and Slovakia.

Session	Date + Time	Topics	Experts delivering the program
Startday 1	Sept 28 - 2023 09.00 - 15.00 h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General • Process • Nutrition • Behavior change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderator + Coach • Medical • Project lead/Project lead • Nutrition + pillars
Startday 2	Sept 29 - 2023 09.00 - 15.00 h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General • Process • Pathophysiology • Nutrition • Behavior change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderator + Coach • Medical/Pathophysiology • Project lead/Project lead • Nutrition + pillars
Returnday after 2 weeks	Oct 12 - 2023 09.00 - 15.00 h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General • Process • Medical • Exercise • Behavior change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderator + Coach • Medical/ • Project lead/Project lead • Nutrition + pillars
Returnday after 4 weeks	Nov 2 - 2023 09.00 - 15.00 h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General • Process • Medical • Relaxation • Behavior change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderator + Coach • Medical • Project lead/Project lead • Nutrition + pillars/Nutrition + pillars
Returnday after 8 weeks	Nov 30 - 2023 09.00 - 15.00 h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General • Sleep • Exam • Implementation plan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderator + Coach • Medical • Project lead/Project lead • Nutrition + pillars/Nutrition + pillars

Start day 1

08.15-08.45	Team pre-talk	Team
08.45-09.00	Welcoming participants in ZOOM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome slide in screen 	Team
09.00-09.30	Welcome <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meet the VL team (introducing team members) Get to know Voeding Leeft <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Background VL Why are we here today with each other? Where do we come from? Timeline Get to know the program. Get to know each other <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Break out rooms - 6 min - (get to know each other in small groups by discipline). Today's & program tomorrow Explanation process training Expectations Relaxation exercise 	Project lead Moderator + Coach & Medical Project lead Project lead Moderator + Coach
09.30 - 10.05	Pathophysiology DM2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (part 1) Interactive moments 	Pathophysiology & Medical
10.05-10.15	Break (big timer)	Project lead
10.15 - 11.00	Pathophysiology DM2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (part 2) Interactive moments 	Pathophysiology & Medical
11.00 - 11.10	Snaxercise	Project lead
11.10 - till lunch break	Nutrition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> part 1: underlying pillars 	Nutrition + pillars
12.00 - 13.00	Lunch break depends on the amount of questions	Project lead
13.00 - 13.50	Nutrition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> part 2: current approach 	Nutrition + pillars
13.50 - 14.00	Break (big timer)	Project lead
14.00 - 14.30	Nutrition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> part 3: nutrition principles 	Nutrition + pillars
14.20 - 14.25	Snaxercise	Project lead
14.25 - 14.55	Nutrition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> part 4: nutrition principles if time - break out rooms per country <i>Question: which opportunities & barriers do you see for implementing after hearing the theory of nutrition?</i> 	Nutrition + pillars

14.55- 15.00	Closing Planning next day	Project lead
--------------	------------------------------	--------------

Start day 2

08.30 - 09.00	Team pre-talk	Team
09.00 - 09.15	Opening <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Question in chat about yesterday • Basic moderations 	Project lead
09.15 - 09.20	Relaxation exercise	Project lead
09.20 - 10.00	Process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction materials • Introduction pilot implementation plan • Introduction program RD2N • community 	Project lead
10.00 - 10.45	Nutrition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repetition of basics (day 1) • Practical information part 1 	Nutrition + pillars
10.45 - 11.00	Break + snaxercise	Project lead
11.00 - 12.00	Nutrition part 4 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reading labels + supermarket safari • Rebuilding recipes 	Nutrition + pillars
12.00 - 12.45	Lunch break	Project lead
12.45 - 13.45	Behavior change <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basics & theory 	Moderator + Coach
13.45 - 13.50	Break	
13.50 - 14.50	Behavior change <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cases & break out rooms 	Moderator + Coach
14.50 - 15.00	Closing	Project lead

Return day after 2 weeks

08.30 - 09.00	Team pre-talk	Team
09.00 - 09.10	Welcome & opening	Project lead
09.10 - 09.15	Relaxation exercise	Moderator + Coach
09.15 - 10.35	Pillar Exercise <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Snaxercise in between 	Nutrition + pillars
10.35 - 10:45	Break	Project lead
10.45 - 12.00	Behavior change	Moderator + Coach
12.00 - 13.00	Lunch break	Project lead
13.00 - 13.15	Process <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you need to begin 	Project lead
13.15 - 14.00	Medical part 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusion process 	Medical
13.45 - 14.00	Break	Project lead

14.00 - 14.50	Medical part 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cases • Break out rooms • Q&A 	Medical
14.50 - 15.00	Closing	Project lead

Return day after 4 weeks

08.30 - 09.00	Team pre-talk	Team
09.00 - 09.10	Welcome & opening <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic moderations 	Project lead
09.10 - 09.15	Relaxation exercise	Project lead
09.15 - 10.00	Process <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • communication • data & evaluation • after care phase • action implementation plan 	Project lead
10.00 - 10.45	Medical part 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reducing medication 	Medical
10.45 - 11.00	Break	Project lead
11.00 - 12.00	Medical part 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cases • Break out rooms • Elk land terughalen met korte recap Recap exercise	Medical
12.00 - 13.00	Lunch break	
13.00 - 13.00	Pillar Relaxation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • part 1 	Nutrition + pillars
13.30 - 13.35	Break	
13.35 - 14.05	Pillar Relaxation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • part 2 	Nutrition + pillars
14.05 - 14.55	Behavior change <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cases 	Moderator + Coach

Return day after 8 weeks

08.30 - 09.00	Team pre-talk	Team
09.00 - 09.05	Welcome & opening <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic moderations 	Project lead
09.05 - 09.15	Relaxation exercise	Moderator + Coach
09.15 - 10.30	Pillar Sleep	Nutrition + pillars
10.30 - 10.45	Break + snaxercise	Project lead
10.45-11.30	Exam	Nutrition + pillars & Project lead
11.30-11.45	Results & introduction presentations action plan afternoon	Project lead
11.45 - 12.45	Lunch break	

12.45 - 13.15	Country 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10 minutes presentation • 10 minutes break out rooms countries separated • 10 minutes asking questions & grades 	Team
13.15 - 13.45	Country 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10 minutes presentation • 10 minutes break out rooms countries separated • 10 minutes asking questions & grades 	Team
13.45 - 14.15	Country 3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10 minutes presentation • 10 minutes break out rooms countries separated • 10 minutes asking questions & grades 	Team
14.15 - 14.45	Country 4 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10 minutes presentation • 10 minutes break out rooms countries separated • 10 minutes asking questions & grades 	Team
14.45 - 15.00	Closing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Certification 	Team

ANNEX 2. OVERVIEW OF VL TRAINING MATERIALS

Material overview Pilot implementation & Train the trainer

Overview of materials shared during training and for pilot implementation

November 2023

This document gives a summary of what materials are shared in the training and for pilot implementation.

- Materials shared during and part of the training

Presentations

Presentations were shared on each of the 5 training days. See below the themes of each presentation shared.

- Startday 1

Themes: Type 2 Diabetes pathophysiology, Nutrition, Introduction Reverse Diabetes2 Now

- Startday 2

Themes: Nutrition, Behavior change, in depth overview Reverse Diabetes2 Now program

- Return day 2 weeks

Themes: Exercise, recruitment & registration, medical inclusion, program content, behavior change

- Return day 4 weeks

Themes: medication reduction, relaxation, data, evaluation, aftercare program and communication during program

- Return day 8 weeks

Themes: Sleep

Other materials

- Pilot implementation plan

On the last training day each country presented the actions for implementing the pilot. For the presentation on what you need for the implementation of a successful pilot a framework overview was developed.

- Reports & articles

Regarding questions of countries during training on guidelines and scientific foundation extra reports and articles were shared as for example more information on financial impact Reverse Diabetes2 Now.

- Exam

An exam was made for the last training day for knowledge testing on the presentations and information shared during the training.

- Certificates

Participants received a certificate after successfully completing the training.

- Materials shared for pilot implementation

All the materials for pilot implementation are explained during the train the trainer program. We divided the materials into 6 chapters. See below the schematic overview of which materials can be used during which stage of the pilot implementation. Be aware that these materials are connected to the train the trainer program and not a substitution of the training. The materials are divided into the following chapters:

- Chapter 1 - BLUE - Recruitment & Registration
- Chapter 2 - PINK - Content during the program
- Chapter 3 - YELLOW - Communication
- Chapter 4 - RED - Medical
- Chapter 5 - GREEN - General
- Chapter 6 - BROWN - Data & Evaluation

Chapter 1 – BLUE. Recruitment & registration

All materials included in this chapter can be used for the recruitment of the support team and recruitment and inclusion of (potential) participants.

What is included and when to use?

Use for the recruitment of the support team:

- Job profiles

Description of profiles and qualifications of different roles in the program team; coach, dietician, nurse, general practitioner and program coordinator.

Use for the recruitment of (potential) participants:

- Recruitment strategies

Information about possible ways to inform patients about the program and steps for recruitment.

Use as a guide for which steps (potential) participants take before the start of the program:

- Patient flow

Schematic overview of the required steps from registration of potential participants to scheduling and confirmation of participation in the program.

Use for the registration for (potential) participants:

- Registration form part 1

First part of the application form with questions about lifestyle habits and motivation. To be filled in by the participant hard copy or online.

- Registration form part 2

Second part of the application form with questions about medical history. To be filled in and signed by the lead practitioner hard copy or online.

Use for inclusion of (potential) participants:

- Inclusion protocol

A general description about the inclusion and exclusion criteria and the purpose and required information for inclusion.

Chapter 2 – PINK. Content

All materials included in this chapter can be used by developing the program and program content for participants.

Use for the development of planning program days:

- General handbook

Timetable of all program days and program components. Learning objectives for the participants per program day are included.

- Coach handbook

Handbook for the coach professional, with in depth information about behavior change, exercises and tools.

Use for the development of program content:

- Presentations

Examples of presentations given during all program days about pathophysiology, nutrition, exercise, sleep and relaxation.

- Participants workbook

Workbook participants receive at the start of the program, with information, explanation, writing assignments and room to record progress.

- Online community

One page explanation about the functions and tools of the online community in the Reverse Diabetes2 Now program.

- Overview learning objectives participants

Table with all learning objectives described for participants in the program.

- Animations

Examples of informative animations of program content shared online.

Use for the development of recipes:

- Recipe book

Booklet with tips, grocery list and 28 everyday recipes for breakfast, lunch and diner.

- Recipe movies

Examples of short video clips with step-by-step guidance in how to prepare the recipes.

Chapter 3 – YELLOW. Communication

All materials included in this chapter can be used for communication purposes with participants and lead practitioners.

3.A. Communication with participants

Use for an overview of tasks in program coordination and communication:

- PC communication tasks

List of all tasks in the order of the timeline, including all communication between program days.

Use for communication with participants between program days:

- Email communication with participants

Examples given for email participants' communication with all the information about the program and sessions.

3.B. Communication with health care professionals

Use for mail communication with health care professionals

- Email communication with the patient's lead practitioner (healthcare professional)

Examples given of email communication with lead practitioner during program

CHAPTER 4 – RED. Medical aspects

All materials included in this chapter can be used by the medical supervision and guidance in the program.

Use for substantiation reducing medication

- Adapting diabetes medication

A practical guide for reducing medication

Use for correct measurement output during program days:

- Measurement instructions

Instructions for measuring waist circumference, weight, blood glucose and HbA1c.

Use for information about the participant medical safety:

- Participant safety

Describes relevant topics for participant safety including safety incident reporting process and calamity process.

CHAPTER 5 – GREEN. General

In this chapter general documents can be found ranging from background information to the privacy statement.

Use for the scientific foundation of the lifestyle program:

- Literature list

Literature list for the scientific foundation of the program.

Use as background information:

- Presentation kick off meeting

Presentation given during the kick off meeting in Oviedo, Spain. Background information on Voeding Leeft and basic information about the program can be found in this presentation.

- Flyer Train The Trainer

Invitation for the Train The Trainer program with basic information on the training.

- Vision & mission Voeding Leeft

Background information, description of the mission, vision, principles, results and goals.

Use for better understanding as an example of the labor hours for the support team:

- Support team hours

The hours of every role in the support team. Be aware that these are the hours of the program at this point for Reverse Diabetes2 Now in the Netherlands and not for a pilot group where the hours could be more or less depending on program design and patient complexity.

Use for better understanding what is needed in a privacy statement:

- Privacy statement & disclaimer

Example privacy statement and disclaimer

Use for getting to know the ICT systems:

- ICT systems

Overview of ICT systems current used by Voeding Lefte for the Dutch program.

Chapter 6 – BROWN. Data & evaluation

All materials included in this chapter can be used for better understanding of the data and evaluation part of the lifestyle program.

Use for conducting an evaluation form:

- Evaluation form examples participants

Example of evaluation forms sent after every program session to the participants

- Evaluation form team

Example of an evaluation form for collection feedback from the support team

Use for a timeline of data collection of the measurements

- Measurements during the program

Data collection of measurements during the program and blood values

Use for collection data for quality of life

- Quality of life questionnaire

Questionnaire with questions about the quality of life of participants

ANNEX 3. EXAMPLE MATERIALS SHARED BY VOEDING LEEFT

An example of the materials used by VL are shown in this Annex.

In this public deliverable it is not possible to share all the materials used by VL. These have been used for teaching purposes, and their publication outside the context of a training course is not allowed by the owner of the BP.

RESULTS AFTER 24-MONTHS

9 out of 10 participants fully or partly reverse diabetes 2

7 out of 10 stopped using insulin

Average weight loss 7kg

Improved quality of life and more energy

Han took part in Reverse Diabetes 2 Now in 2016

“Because of Reverse Diabetes2 Now I have another life. I have lost 16kg and haven't used any diabetes medication for 7years. I feel like a young man again!”

Different insulin sensitivity of different organs

The liver also produces glucose when the blood sugar level is low

= **gluconeogenesis**

When the liver becomes insulin resistant, it is less able to identify (high) levels of blood sugar and as a result keeps producing glucose → thereby contributing to higher (fasting) glucose

Take home messages

1. Insulin resistance is the main problem in type 2 diabetes
2. Insulin resistance occurs in 2 phases: hyperinsulinemia followed by less secretion of insulin (beta cell dysfunction)
3. Insulin resistance in the liver impacts the fasting glucose level
4. Insulin resistance leads to increased triglyceride levels in the blood and liver fattening
5. Hyperinsulinemia accelerates insulin resistance and makes people tired and hungry

But there is more - type 2 diabetes is multifactorial

Where **insulin resistance** is the main problem

Carbohydrate-rich food gives greatest insulin production

Blood glucose

Insulin

Individual communication with participants

- Self management asked of the participant
- Participant is responsible for own process
- Participant keeps team up to date (lifestyle anamnese/day curve)

Team provides feedback and answers questions on request participant

Our main channels of communication 1-1:

- E-mail
- Phone

Optimization of the gut microbiota

Probiotic food: foods with live bacteria

- Fermented food: yoghurt, farmers cheese, tempéh, miso, sauerkraut

Prebiotic food: food for the bacteria in the gut

- Fibre from vegetables and fruit. Mainly: onion, leek, garlic, chicory, artichoke, asparagus

Topics we are going to discuss today

1. Recap: Type 2 diabetes pathophysiology
2. Recap: nutrition principles of Reverse Diabetes2 Now
3. Recap: the underlying pillars
4. Reading labels + supermarkt safari
5. Recipe building + how to change your favorite recipes according to the guidelines?

3. Maslow learning cycle - phases in behaviour change

1. Recognise your patterns
 2. Clarify why you do what you do
 3. Visualize where you want to move to
 4. Focus on what is important to you: every choice you make has an effect
 5. Dare to move out of your comfort zone
 6. Experiment and create new patterns
 7. Be your own researcher: examine your own behaviour, experience what happens in your body, keep data
 8. Train, train and keep training
 9. Get up when you have fallen
 10. Celebrate your successes
-

Materials

The participant receives in the Reverse Diabetes2 Now program:

Recommended to start with:

- Blood glucose meter
- Participant book

Why is exercise so important in type 2 diabetes?

1. Makes cells more sensitive to insulin and ensure glucose is absorbed more easily
2. Good for recovery by creating new blood vessels
3. Stimulates the production of many hormones in the brain
4. Stimulates the production of new nerve cells and connections in the brain
5. Reduces inflammation
6. **Improves diversity and variety of gut bacteria**

Before program:

Medication: Metformin 1000 mg 3 times per day

- Weight: 95 kg en BMI: 29.2
- Waist circumference: 100 cm
- HbA1c: 69 mmol/mol (8,5%)
- eGFR > 60
- No other medical issues

4-point day curve

- Fasting glucose: 10.8
- Before lunch: 12.5
- Before dinner: 11.6
- Prior to sleep: 11.9

Question 5.

What do you think of the fasting glucose value?

What medication changes should be made?

Results after two weeks:

- Weight: 92 kg (3 kg reduction)
- Waist circumference: 97 cm (3 cm reduction)
- Fasting glucose: 10.4 (0.4 reduction)
- He didn't experience any hypo- or hyperglycemia during the week

4-point day curve

- Fasting glucose: 10.2
- Before lunch: 7.4
- Before dinner: 7.8
- Prior to sleep: 7.1

Question 6.

What is your opinion about the 4-point day curve?

How does the fasting glucose value relate to the other values during the day?

Can you explain this?

The relationship between (chronic) stress and type 2 diabetes long term

Sleep hygiene

=All behaviours concerning or preceding going to bed
Optimizing sleep hygiene can lead to better sleep quality
Several factors are important to take into account:

- caffeine intake
- body temperature
- room temperature
- decreasing stimuli
- daily schedule
- relaxation (brain waves)
- screen time
- circadian rhythm

How to fall asleep: two systems

Disclaimer. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

The project CARE4DIABETES has received funding from the European Commission under GA No 101082427.